

INFLUENCE OF PROJECT LEADERSHIP ON PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION BY MINISTRY OF HEALTH AND SANITATION SERVICES IN TURKANA COUNTY, KENYA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10203836>

Published Date: 24-November-2023

Abstract: Projects can fail for a variety of reasons, which present themselves in different ways and at different stages of the project. A huge number of health initiatives launched by the Turkana County government are facing significant scheduling and financial management issues. As a result, the project takes longer than expected, increasing the associated expenditures. Furthermore, the projected benefits are only partially or never achieved as a result of a variety of poor project implementations. Therefore, this study sought to investigate the influence of project leadership on project implementation by ministry of health and sanitation services in Turkana County, Kenya. The descriptive research design was adopted in the study. The study's target population consisted of ten health initiatives run by the Ministry of Health and Sanitation in Turkana County, Kenya. There were 55 responders, including 5 project managers and 40 project team members. Because the population is small, the study relied on a census of 55 people. Structured questionnaires were used to obtain primary data for the investigation. Six respondents participated in a pilot research conducted by the Ministry of Public Works in Turkana County. The content validity test was used to assess the validity of research instruments. Cronbach's alpha was utilized to calculate a correlation coefficient to evaluate the research instrument's internal consistency. To evaluate quantitative data, descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used. The study also used inferential statistics, such as multiple regression analysis. According to the findings of the study, project leadership had a positive and significant impact on the project implementation by the Ministry of Health and Sanitation Services in Turkana County, Kenya. The study finds that project leadership is a social influence process focused on maximizing a team's efforts to attain a goal. According to the study, in order to ensure project success, the leader's approach should be adaptable, collaborative, and innovative.

Keywords: Project Leadership, Project Implementation.

1. INTRODUCTION

Project implementation involves the direct supervision of a project to ensure that it aligns with the objectives specified in the planning phase. This occurs during the planning phase, when a team establishes the project's primary objectives, as well as the timeline and financial resources (Slevin & Pinto, 2017). According to Mahfuth, Loulizi, Alhallaq, and Tayeh (2019), the project manager assesses the team's adherence to the project objectives during the implementation phase and makes necessary adjustments to keep the project on course. Consequently, project managers must effectively execute a project in order to deliver the required outcomes and satisfy the project's clients or primary stakeholders.

A thorough grasp of all project management phases is required for successful project implementation, and each phase has its own set of needs that aid in project implementation (Kuruppuarachchi, Mandal, & Smith, 2018). Most projects, according to Mobey and Parker (2020), are complicated and demanding, necessitating a delicate balance of meeting user needs, staying within budget, utilizing resources, staying within scope, maintaining quality, and completing on time. A decent project

would be impossible to accomplish without a structured approach to all of these issues. As a result, a robust and well-structured project management technique will go a long way toward assuring project success.

The implementation of development projects is crucial to a country's achievement of its development goals. A fraction of development projects in Pakistan are delayed due to cost and time overruns, which must be addressed through an integrated and comprehensive plan (Shah, Khan, & Khalil, 2019). According to Rehman, Khan, and Khan (2021), Pakistani government initiatives are sometimes organized on the basis of socio-political goals, employment creation, and sub-optimal resource allocation, which affects the successful implementation of such programs. As a result, an appropriate strategy will help Pakistan accomplish its national goals by optimizing the implementation of development projects.

According to the research conducted by Akande, Olagunju, Aremu, and Ogundepo (2018), the persistent lack of success and ultimate desertion of diverse development initiatives in developing nations has reached such a prominent level that Nigeria has been encompassed within this predicament. This can be attributed to the prevailing social and political frameworks, cultural impediments, and an insufficiency of monetary backing within the public sector of Nigeria, all of which have hampered efficient project planning and implementation. According to Igwe and Ude (2018), Nigeria has beautifully devised concepts, but the government has ineffectively implemented initiatives. The main reasons are institutional inefficiency in project implementation, a lack of vision, and insufficient budgetary allocations, which result in exorbitant project finance costs and, in the long run, corruption. As a result, enhanced effective and efficient project management procedures are required to ensure the successful implementation of these projects.

In Kenya, the devolution of health-care functions has led in a variety of outcomes, particularly in health-care programs. The unequal allocation of human resources for health has had a negative influence on County governments' implementation of health care projects, delaying access to health care services in the country's rural locations (Gitonga & Keiyyoro, 2017). Similarly, Abdi and Gakuu (2020) report that poor financial planning and insufficient local taxation systems, as well as hospital personnel, have hampered Kenyan county governments' adoption of health care and provision of health services.

Shanks (2019) provides a definition for project implementation as the execution of a project plan with the aim of producing deliverables, which can be products or services, for clients or stakeholders. According to Crawford and Bryce (2019), the objective of project implementation is to translate the action plan into practice, generate the desired outcomes, accomplish the intended purpose(s), and effectively contribute to the overall project goal. It also involves efficient management of available resources, as well as monitoring and reporting on progress. Consequently, successful project implementation necessitates the revision of stakeholder analysis to ensure the inclusion of all necessary parties, reevaluating project risks, and continuously monitoring and evaluating the project's advancement towards its objectives.

Project management practices are the underlying concerns inherent in the project that must be maintained in order for the project to be performed quickly and effectively (Davies, Doyle, & Doyle, 2017). According to Attarzadeh and Ow (2018), project management is the process of controlling the achievement of project objectives in project implementation. Using the company's present organizational structures and resources, it aims to manage the project using a range of tools and methodologies while minimizing disruption to the company's routine activities. As a result, project management methods are important because they outline what is expected of the task, the scope of the job, the allocation of necessary resources, the execution process planning, monitoring work progress, and modifying changes that may emerge from the initial plan.

Project leadership is the discipline that encompasses both the artistic and scientific aspects of guiding a team towards the triumphant culmination of a project. By uniting individuals with a shared objective, project leadership guarantees that the team achieves greater success collectively than they would individually (Podgorska & Pichlak, 2019). According to Shenhar (2021), a project leader keeps their team interested and ensures that each task is accomplished flawlessly during the development process. They strive to avoid time delays and cost overruns while also ensuring delivery quality. As a result, project management leadership is a required skill for guiding the project to completion, and it requires the leader to demonstrate a wide range of competencies and behaviors.

The Turkana County Integrated Development Plan (CIDP II) for 2018-2022 provides as a comprehensive roadmap to help the Turkana County Vision be realized. Turkana County strives to provide opportunities for social empowerment for all women and men, as well as food, nutritional, and water security, good health and well-being, education, and economic prosperity, all while living in a peaceful, socially just, and culturally sensitive environment supported by a resilient natural resource base and the highest integrity inclusive governance. Preventive, promotional, curative, and rehabilitative healthcare

services are provided by the County Ministry of Health and Sanitation Services. This is based on Kenya's 2010 constitution, Vision 2030, Kenya Health Sector Strategy Plan 2012-2030, and UN Sustainable Development Goal 3 to ensure the provision of quality health care services and, as a result, a healthy and productive country.

Since the introduction of devolved governments in Kenya in 2013, Turkana County Department of Health has been managing the county's health sector to deliver the constitutional mandate driven by the concepts of collaborative planning, monitoring, and execution. The County aspires to be a healthy and productive county built on a progressive, responsive, and long-term health system that is evidence-based and client-centered. This guiding concept complements the county health sector's vision statement and commitment to speeding Universal Health Coverage (UHC) achievement, as well as the HSSP's strategic orientation.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Project implementation measurement is essential in project management because it enables the project manager to detect budget and scope issues and develop appropriate solutions to address these issues (Matavire, Chigona, & Abu, 2018). Organizations work in an uncertain environment, according to Aldabbus (2020), and project implementations are subject to a range of external influences, unplanned occurrences, ever-growing requirements, shifting restrictions, and variable resource flows. Furthermore, insufficient information and ineffective project management resulted not only in project cost overruns and completion delays, but also in project termination before completion.

A large number of health projects initiated by the Turkana County government face major scheduling and financial management challenges. As a result, project completion takes longer than projected, raising the associated costs. Furthermore, due to a number of poor project implementations, the anticipated benefits are only partially or never realized. Statistics show, for example, that projects such as the County Referral Hospital, the establishment of a Turkana County Medical Supplies unit, investment in the development of a critical mass of Medical and Nutrition specialists, and strengthening disease surveillance systems in Turkana County have not been completed on time, and the majority of them are still in the planning stages.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical Literature Review

Resource Based View

According to Wernerfelt's (1984) resource-based view theory, a corporation is a combination of organizational resources, human capital resources, and physical capital resources. Resources can be both tangible and intangible. As the firm's effectiveness grows, so does the set of resources available to it. Individual resources may not be sufficient to provide a competitive advantage. Competitive advantages are created by the synergistic combination and integration of resource sets. Furthermore, Wernerfelt (1995) defines theory as a project management theory that is extensively used in project management. It looks into how resources can be leveraged to gain a competitive advantage.

This theory is relevant to the study because it shows how the County government manages projects depending on its resources and expertise. The County's resource must be precious, rare, and imperfectly imitable and substitutable in order to be a source of effective execution of their health projects. Furthermore, by prioritizing project demands, project managers can learn how to employ existing resources, select suppliers, and conduct contract reviews to efficiently finish and implement a specific project.

Empirical Literature Review

Ogohi and Ogochukwu (2016) investigated the influence of project managers' leadership styles on project implementation in their research study. In order to supplement their primary data, they utilized a variety of secondary sources, such as textbooks authored by various individuals on the topic, scholarly journals, reputable magazines, online information, and both published and unpublished materials pertaining to the field. The data was subjected to analysis employing the content analysis approach, which was chosen due to its reliance on a thorough examination of the data's content heavily on secondary source data. This study discovered a link between management leadership styles and project implementation, with project management control having the greatest influence on project performance.

Omony's (2019) research investigated the role of project leadership in mitigating the impact of complexity on the success of Kenyan public infrastructure megaprojects. The investigation was designed as a multi-method investigation. A census survey of 124 respondents was conducted using three interconnected questionnaires based on 31 completed public infrastructure megaprojects. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to examine the quantitative data, while scenario mapping and triangulation were used to analyze the qualitative data. Project leadership had a strong positive influence on project execution, such that when the leadership style moved to complexity leadership, the success rate increased.

Mbogoh, Mukulu, and Waiganjo (2019) investigated project leadership as a predictor of project implementation in Kenyan grass-roots support Non-Governmental Organizations. The study used a cross-sectional survey research method. The study's target population was 500 employees from Grass-Roots Support NGOs in Embu County. Stratified sampling was used to choose the sample from the Target Population. Questionnaires, an interview guide, and an observation form were used to collect data. Descriptive statistics and regression analysis were used to analyze the data. It was shown that there is a considerable favorable relationship between project leadership and project implementation.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The descriptive research design was adopted in the study. The study's target population consisted of ten health initiatives run by the Ministry of Health and Sanitation in Turkana County, Kenya. There were 55 responders, including 5 project managers and 40 project team members. Because the population is small, the study relied on a census of 55 people. Structured questionnaires were used to obtain primary data for the investigation. Six respondents participated in a pilot research conducted by the Ministry of Public Works in Turkana County. The content validity test was used to ensure the validity of the research tools. Cronbach's alpha was utilized to calculate a correlation coefficient to examine the internal consistency of the study instrument. To examine quantitative data, descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were employed. Inferential statistics, such as multiple regression analysis, were also used in the study. Tables and figures were employed to present the outcomes of the data analysis.

4. FINDINGS

The descriptive statistics results of project leadership are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Project Leadership

Statement	M	SD
Planning assists the team in staying focused on the objectives and the end goal.	3.96	0.445
Project managers use planning to keep track of which resources have been assigned and so avoid over-allocation.	4.43	1.219
Project organization leads to the development of good teamwork and teams that identify fully with project objectives.	4.78	0.782
The project organization guarantees that projects are completed on time.	4.10	1.670
Providing guidance during project execution tries to combine all individual efforts by coordinating them properly.	4.69	0.579

The results in Table 1 indicate that the respondents strongly agreed on the statements that project organization leads to the development of good teamwork and teams that identify fully with project objectives ($M=4.78$, $SD=0.782$) and that providing guidance during project execution tries to combine all individual efforts by coordinating them properly ($M=4.69$, $SD=0.579$). These findings are consistent with those of Ogohi and Ogochukwu (2016), who evaluated the impact of project managers' leadership styles on project implementation. This study discovered a link between management leadership styles and project implementation, with project management control having the greatest influence on project performance.

The results in Table 1 also indicate that respondents agreed on the statements that project managers use planning to keep track of which resources have been assigned and so avoid over-allocation ($M=4.43$, $SD=1.219$), the project organization guarantees that projects are completed on time ($M=4.10$, $SD=1.670$) and that planning assists the team in staying focused on the objectives and the end goal ($M=3.96$, $SD=0.445$). These findings are consistent with those of a study conducted by Mbogoh, Mukulu, and Waiganjo (2019) that focused on project leadership as a determinant of project execution in Kenyan grass-roots support Non-Governmental Organizations and discovered a positive significant relationship between project leadership and project implementation.

5. RESULTS OF REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.945 ^a	.893	.886	.179

The adjusted R², also known as the coefficient of multiple determinations, is the percentage of the variance in the dependent explained individually or jointly by the independent variables, as shown in Table 2. The corrected R² result shows that the project leadership variable explains 0.886 of the variations in project implementation by the Ministry of Health and Sanitation Services in Turkana County, Kenya. This suggests that unstudied variables contribute to a factor of 0.114 of project implementation.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.964	1	14.964	72.116	.000 ^a
	Residual	10.790	52	.208		
	Total	24.754	53			

The value 0.000a indicates that the significance level is less than 0.05, indicating that the model's statistical significance on how the project leadership variable studied affects project implementation by the Ministry of Health and Sanitation Services in Turkana County, Kenya. The data also show that at the 5% significance level, the statistical value of F was more than the statistical mean value ($102.407 > 3.741$), supporting the model's relevance.

Table 4: Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.646	.223		2.897	.000
	Project leadership	0.784	.042	4.208	18.667	.000

According to Table 4, project implementation by the Ministry of Health and Sanitation Services in Turkana County, Kenya would be 64.6% if project leadership remained constant. A unit increase in project leadership will result in a 78.4% increase in project implementation by the Ministry of Health and Sanitation Services in Turkana County, Kenya. This produced the regression equation shown below.

$$\text{Project implementation} = 0.646 + 0.784 (\text{project leadership})$$

In addition, the study revealed that project leadership had a positive and significant relationship on the project implementation by ministry of health and sanitation services in Turkana County, Kenya as shown by t values ($t=18.667, <0.005$).

6. CONCLUSIONS

The study finds that project leadership is a social influence process focused on maximizing a team's efforts to attain a goal. It entails developing a concept, encouraging people to participate with it, managing delivery, and assembling a team that works cohesively toward a common vision. Organizations rely largely on project managers' good leadership qualities to monitor, assess, plan, and maintain compliance with company goals and objectives. Being a successful project leader requires a variety of skills, including planning, organization, management, budgeting, monitoring, testing, and project implementation.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

According to the study, the leader's approach should be adaptable, collaborative, and imaginative in order to assure project success. At the same time, the leader should encourage team development and motivation so that the varied individuals can work as a team. The leader should drive the team and stakeholders through a fine-tuned project study during the project's

planning phase to better understand the project's requirements. Leading a project to completion requires management to complete the team members' tasks in an efficient and effective manner. It requires the individual to have a clear vision, purpose, and the ability to attract talented and efficient employees.

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